

Identification of Passive Macro-Models for High-Speed Interconnects operating in non-TEM conditions

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Abstract — The efficient simulation of high-speed interconnects demands compact macro-models. For interconnects operating in non-TEM conditions, the accurate identification of such passive macro-models is still a challenge. We consider the application of Vector Fitting and of a suitable passivity enforcement procedure for the identification of macro-models of such class of interconnects. The corresponding time domain model is then used for signal integrity analysis.

Keywords — Reduced Order Model, Transmission Lines, High-Speed Interconnects.

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate modelling of electrical interconnects is required in the design of the modern electronic systems to address several signal integrity issues. Lumped macro-models, which enable fast time domain simulations through recursive convolutions, are usually generated deriving a rational approximation of the transfer matrix used to describe the considered structures. The identification of the rational approximation is pursued with some least square algorithm, starting from measured or simulated port responses. It is widespread opinion that the Vector Fitting algorithm (VF) [1], which is an iterative least square fitting algorithm with a reliable pole relocation scheme, provides a more robust approach as compared to older algorithms (standard Sanathanan-Koerner method [2] and Model Based Parameter Estimation [3]). Such robustness is mainly due to the use of simple fraction as basis functions, avoiding power of frequency, which easily lead to ill-conditioned numerical formulations. Furthermore, the stability enforcement (i.e. poles having negative real part) is trivially achievable by mirroring the unstable poles, which may appear during the iterations, in the left half plane.

After the identification, a second fundamental issue has to be addressed that is the passivity enforcement. Roughly speaking, passivity indicates the inability of a structure to generate energy. Passive structures, such as interconnects, have to be described through passive macro-models, since a non-passive model may lead to unstable transient simulations depending on its termination networks [4-5].

In this work we address the model order reduction issue, for some high-speed interconnects operating in non-TEM conditions. In particular we will focus on the case reported in [6] to further improve them, both from the accuracy point of view as well as considering the issue of passivity enforcement.

II. ISSUES IN THE IDENTIFICATION OF WIDE BAND MACROMODELS FOR HIGH SPEED INTERCONNECTS

Electrically long interconnects can be correctly modelled with the transmission line model until the quasi-TEM hypothesis of

propagation holds. When a time-domain analysis is required (because of the large frequency ranges and the nonlinear behaviour of terminal devices), an efficient characterization of the transmission line is provided by the popular Method of Characteristics (MoC), which describes the line by means of the characteristic admittance and the propagation function. Qualitative information on such a model allows the analytical extraction of the irregular terms of these functions (such as the delays involved in the propagation function). In this way, the identification process reduces to an almost trivial rational approximation of the remainders of both describing operators, which are smooth functions [7]. In many practical VLSI applications, the bandwidth of signals carried by the electrical interconnects extends to frequency ranges where the quasi-TEM assumption does no longer holds. In such cases, the transmission line model is inadequate to catch those high-frequency effects, like radiation and dispersion, which actually affect the system performance. A full-wave analysis would be, in principle, necessary to correctly describe the structure behaviour. However, it has been recently shown the possibility to extend the validity of the transmission line model to frequency ranges where their smallest characteristic wavelength approaches the conductor separation. An enhanced transmission line model has been proposed in [8], where the effects of such high-frequencies on the propagation performance have been deeply investigated in the frequency-domain. In [6] a first attempt has been made to obtain a time-domain characterization and to perform signal integrity analysis. However, the macro-modelling of such structures is still a challenge. In fact, when the physics of the propagation does not enable the use of the Method of Characteristics, macro-models have to be derived from a characterization given as transfer function matrix, typically made of non-smooth frequency responses holding delays (i.e. non-minimum phase shift functions). Difficulties related to wide band identifications of such responses can limit their usefulness in signal integrity analysis. When considering such kind of interconnects, firstly it is difficult when not impossible to identify directly the whole transfer matrix, so that the components are identified each one in one step resulting in different poles. As a second drawback, the passivity violations appear to be difficult to remove.

III. PASSIVITY ENFORCEMENT ON WIDE BAND MACROMODELS

Passivity property of a multi-port circuit is equivalent to the conditions that its transfer matrix is *positive real*, in case of hybrid representation (impedance or admittance representations), or *bounded real*, in case of scattering representation [9]. These conditions can be directly applied

for testing passivity, but require a frequency sweep since they need to be checked at any frequency. This implies that a not accurate sampling of the frequency axis, could give a wrong result.

Dealing with VF algorithm, rational transfer matrices identified could not satisfy the mentioned properties even if original data do, so passivity should be checked and eventually enforced, correcting the macro-model at those frequencies where violations are found. Moreover, passivity violations can also arise in the original data, when the electromagnetic model adopted is known as inconsistent in some frequencies band, such as in [6]. The ETL model is a full-wave model based on the assumption that the terminal devices interact with the interconnect only through the terminal currents and voltages. For such a reason, it is neglected the contribution of the currents along the devices to the vector potential used to characterize the line itself. This could give rise to bands of passivity violation, whose position can be easily predicted [8].

In the full paper we will address this issue, showing a proper approach suitable to correct the non-passive model. The proposed technique [4-5] will be both evaluated to find out a suitable procedure for the solution of the specific problem.

IV. TEST CASES

We will show two case studies. Case-study 1 considers two square conductors widely separated, with $a=1\text{mm}$, $b=1\text{mm}$, $h_c=10\text{mm}$, and a length of $2l=100\text{mm}$. Case-study 2, instead, refers to a condition when the proximity effect is not negligible, assuming $b=2a=2\text{mm}$, $h_c=2\text{mm}$ and a length of $2l=30\text{mm}$. Impedances matrices of such interconnects have been obtained through a computer code based on the enhanced transmission line model [6]. Figures 2 and 3 show the identification of the magnitude of both Z_{self} and Z_{mutual} referring to the test case 1. Although the passivity violation in the original model, mentioned in the previous paragraph, have been subjected to compensation before to fit the responses, the reduced model still exhibit violations, which need to be removed in a further step [4-5].

Fig. 1 Reference geometry for the considered case-studies.

Fig. 2 Identification of magnitude of Z_{self} , case 1.

Fig. 3 Identification of the magnitude of Z_{mutual} , case 1.

V. REFERENCES

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